

QUIZ**LAST NAME: NALUMANSI****FIRST NAME: BERNADETTE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: DR KABIRU GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 11)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. The most common research questions in academic work **Conceptual¹** Practical Speculative Applied

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed., edited by Wayne C. Booth, et al., (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

2. **The following sentence is not true about visual presentation of data**

- Area chart compares one variable across a series of cases²**
- Scatterplots compare two variables at multiple data points for a single case
- Bubble charts compare three variables at multiple data points for a single case
- Bubble charts compare three variables at one data point for multiple cases

3. **The basic pattern for citations in the bibliography style, includes all the following except**

- Parenthetical citations³**
- Full notes
- Parenthetical notes
- Bibliography entries

4. **Below are the aims of the conclusion chapter in a study except**

- To put the research in the context of other research⁴**
- To leave readers with a clear idea of the study claim
- Make readers understand the study's importance
- To suggest further research

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 66

³ Ibid., 102.

⁴ Ibid., 170.

5. **A qualitative research approach focused on intensive description and analysis of a phenomenon, social unit or system bounded by time and place is**

- Case study⁵**
- Phenomenological study
- Ethnographic study
- Grounded Theory

6. **In these qualitative research traditions, literature review is conducted both before and after data collection**

- Case study and narrative⁶**
- Phenomenology and Ethnography
- Ethnography and grounded theory
- Grounded theory and case study

7. **To answer research questions in qualitative studies, the main areas of information needed are all the following except**

- Descriptive⁷**
- Contextual
- Demographic
- Perceptual

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 11.

⁶ Ibid., 47.

⁷ Ibid., 69.

8. **The standards for convincing qualitative research are the following except**
- Validity⁸**
 - Credibility
 - Transferability
 - Dependability
9. **The primary data analysis approach in grounded theory**
- Open, axial, and selective coding⁹**
 - Detailed description followed by analysis for themes and patterns
 - Generation of meaning units and development of an essence description
 - Cross-sectional analysis
10. **The following statement is not true regarding analytic approaches in qualitative studies**
- Immersion approaches are the most structured and least interpretive¹⁰**
 - Codes are emergent in editing approaches
 - Template approach is less interpretive and flexible than the editing approach
 - Editing approaches are typified by the grounded theory

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 77.

⁹ Ibid., 98.

¹⁰ Ibid., 99.

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